

Semantic Mapping in ENVRI and EPOS

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ENVRI and EPOS

- ENVRI: 27 RIs variously ERICs, Landmarks...
- Atmosphere, Hydrosphere, Geosphere, Biosphere
- EPOS: 1 RI (ERIC)
 - ~250 asset suppliers
 - Central homogeneous rich metadata catalog
 - Ingestion through conversion of ~17 heterogeneous metadata formats to EPOS-DCAT-AP and hence to CERIF
- ENVRI now building a catalog for all ENVRI RIs based on EPOS technology

Aspects of the work

- **Vocabularies**
- **Harmonisation (as much as possible)**
- **Subset of common terms**
- **Catalog**

Vocabularies

What has been done

Incubator register

Why an intermediate stage?

The entities are defined as concepts with label and description
Relations broader and narrower between entities are done
But everything is mixed up together

Harmonisation

Harmonisation

- Group working on this in EPOS
- And also in other RIs in ENVRI
 - Especially Oceanography (Alexandra Kokkinaki, BODC)
- Very slow and human resource-heavy work
- Is it worth it – should we not do mappings?

Common Subset

Common SUBset

- In ENVRI proposed by oceanography domain (Katrina Exter, VLIZ) for use in the ENVRI catalog
- A very small number of agreed terms common to all subdomains (atmosphere, hydrosphere, geosphere, biosphere)
- Ongoing work, almost complete
- Provides some homogeneity in discovery of digital assets across the heterogeneous subdomains and even more heterogeneous RI digital assets

Catalog

CERIF: the basic model

<https://eurocris.org/services/main-features-cerif>

- **Base entities:** objects in the real world e.g. Asset, Person which have attributes
- **Link Entities:** relationships between base entities with attributes including 'role' and 'temporal duration'

- Example Link entity instance:

• **ASSET** **ROLE** **TEMPORAL INTERVAL**
PERSON

• <Paper X>[<authored by> <19970128 00:00:00><19980812 00:00:00>]<Person P>

• (optionally, also add probability as an attribute – modal logic)

CERIF: syntactic and semantic layers

Layers

- Syntactic layer: referential and functional integrity
- Semantic Layer: semantic consistency and interoperability
- In fact 'authored by' is not represented as a text string in the role attribute of the link entity but as a UUID which points to the semantic layer where a role 'authored by' is stored in a base entity and can be related to textual terms in the same or other base entities by link entities thus allowing full ontological capability including multilinguality (see "scritto da")

Metadata Ingestion Pipeline

Catalog

Extension (gold) DCAT □ EPOS-DCAT-AP
Still being extended towards CERIF completeness

class EPOS-DCAT-AP-Simplified

This is still very much work in progress....

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